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Survey Results for ArboDat+

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Results of the survey

Some introducing words

This is a summary of the Arbodat+ survey as part of NFDI4Objects, which took place between 21 November 2023 and 18 December 2023.

Background:

ArboDat+ is funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) under the National Research Data Infrastructure Germany (NFDI) program. ArboDat+ is a continued development of the ArboDat program and is being carried out as a collaborative project within NFDI4Objects under the scope of Task Area 3 “Analytics & Experiments”, with participation the Lower Saxony Institute for Historical Coastal Research (NIhK) and the Institute of Pre- and Protohistoric Archaeology (UFG) as well as the Department of Computer Science (IfI) at Kiel University. We are working on a novel implementation of the archaeobotanical database program ArboDat, with the aim of promoting its establishment in the national and international community. To this goal, the software will be re-implemented as a more accessible database system. It is also being developed into a more simplified, flexible and multilingual version. However, the functionality and structure of the original program should be widely kept to enable the easy data transfer into ArboDat+. This survey was conducted to promote the contribution of the user community which is very much appreciated and important for this project. Invitations to participate in this survey were sent to these mailing lists relevant to the archaeobotanical community ¹. This ensured that the current national and international user community was addressed.

General remarks:

The survey was conducted using the LimeSurvey-tool and data are stored on NFDI4Objects servers. Individual comments are original and were not corrected (e.g. for typos). In order to avoid doubled or insufficient information being processed, only complete responses were included in the analysis - 30 documents. The responses are analysed by category below.

¹Next to the Arbodat Mailing list, which reaches out to 145 program users, the archaeobotany@jiscmail.ac.uk mailing list has been addressed.

Usage of ArboDat

Question: What is your purpose to use ArboDat?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Data entry
- Make reports
- Scientific analysis
- Publication
- Other

Other:

- ideally access to data from other sites
- schneller Einblick in Daten während der Arbeit (translated by authors: Quick insight into data during work)
- Communication and exchange with other labs
- Archiving own and already published data sets and exchange with other laboratories
- have an overview
- internal archive
- standardized data archiving
- archiving, standardized data
- uniform system for data sharing

Institution

Question: At what kind of institution do you use ArboDat?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Government
- Company
- University
- Research Institute
- Other

Other:

- we also require from companies to use the Program when providing dataset to us
- private study
- commercial archaeology

Language

Question: In which language do you use ArboDat?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- German
- English
- French

Comment:

- Turkish
- I think english works very well everywhere and makes also the entries standatized. We are finally small community and the most use English anyhow. Probably Spanish and Russian can be languages to consider on long term, but I do not need such extensions for my work or the work of our team
- Scandinavian languages
- maybe Chinese, Spanish and Italian
- English
- Italian
- If an additional language is not fluently spoken by the programmers, there is no control the terms used having the same meaning as the German, English or French ones. We had long discussions with the colleagues to understand eachother in terms of archaeology and methodology... Additional languages do not seem to be a “central” task of this project.
- None for my Needs; bioarchaeological terms difficult to translate exactly
- a Dutch translation could be nice but it is not a necessity
- Swedish

Section

Question: Which of the following sections do you use in ArboDat?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Data Entry
- Data Evaluation
- Site Report
- Data Survey

Data entry

Comment by the authors: This question was only visible to users who have chosen to use this section

Missing values

Question: Are there any fields or entry options that are not used, missing or need to be changed when entering data? Questions about the thesaurus and PCODE will follow separately. Please briefly state the most important points in the comments. These should then be used as a basis for the discussion on www.arbodat.info. More detailed information will then also be collected there.

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Project
- Site / -
- Feature
- Sample
- Dating
- Result

Comment by the authors: After publication of the survey, it became apparent from a comment that a mistake had been made. It was asked for the sections “Project” and “Site”. Site is a component/equivalent of Project in ArboDat, so these answers were summarised.

Comment:

Project

- Field for complete citation of publication should be added; “Abk. Fundstelle should allow more letters
- the project field “Abreviation” shall have more characters, “natural unit” is not so useful when having the geographic coordinates and I think those shall be obligatory field
- Bigger field sizes for “Project name” and “Abk. Fundstelle” would be great
- the type of the coordinate system shall be obligatory to enter as well as the coordinates - more and more we need this information for maps , also some directions on the comments on the site: that they are important and appear in the site reports can be added
- a field for the citation of the publication, which can be added in queries involving several sites, would be very useful; being able to have the coordinates in the queries would also be important
- Your questions are not clear. Informations for the project are indispensable
- absolutely necessary
- Would it be possible to connect different projects? We use one project per “excavation year” and sometimes we would then need to seek for several projects to make lists.
- The data field is far too short and should be expanded

Feature

- field for dating should be available (sometimes only features are dated not exactly the sample); “gebäudezugehörig” not necessary
- It is important to record feature types for the data evaluation
- “excavated Area” is rarely used, the feature type shall be obligatory -it is very useful for data evaluation
- the field is good as it is
- adding years of excavation is laborious (especially if including several years), and cannot be transferred, which should be changed
- Your questions are not clear. Informations for the feature are indispensable.
- absolutely necessary
- Could be an overlying optional level between project and feature?
- The data field is too short and should be expanded

Sample

- Verschiedene Labore nutzen oftmals unterschiedliche Fraktionsgrößen; in BaWü z. B. ist die kleinste Fraktion 0.315mm; (translated by author: Different laboratories often use different fraction sizes; in Baden-Württemberg, for example, the smallest fraction is 0.315mm. For example, the smallest fraction is 0.315mm)
- fractions: presetting for all samples of one site would be helpful; maybe not so detailed (org/anorg.; 4 fractions); presetting at “volume” “trocken/feucht” should be preset according to the site
- we never use “Microrest sample” option
- Changeable naming of fields “Stratum, Schicht, Quadrant, Planum” would be nice.
- more options for analyzed fractions needed (e.g. org 0.3, min. 8), a section to note the volume of the fraction
- clutural group is confusing, if it will be kept - probably some link to the program manual can be created? Generally concerning samples and results if linkage of each field to the corresponding field in the manual can be done - will be very useful - also for giving the program to students. It will make it self explaining
- depending on the site, it is not practical to have the dating in the individual samples (although sometimes it is necessary)
- Your questions are not clear. Informations for the sample are indispensable.
- absolutely necessary
- Would there be a possibility to connect Absolute dating with Arch. dating?

Dating

- there is no point in filling in radiocarbon dates, since the software only uses the chronocultural classification
- should be able to use for each sample, but also for feature (see above)
- 1. Field “Material”: Some general choosing options as checkbox/dropdown fields for information like “material (eg plant, bone), preservation (eg charred, mineralized...), maybe also linked to Resttyp”, instead of entering a complete text like “Hordeum vulgare var. vulgare, Korn entspelzt, verkohlt”. 2. Maybe providing a link to a calibration program like Oxcal (and storing the calculated results?) instead of making entries in field “C14 cal BC/AD: (2 sigma)”
- the field can be integrated in the sample with drop down menu? giving lab code result, deviation dated material, keeping the information on absolute dating together with the samples is very useful: to avoid double dating and also to make quick, uncomplicated check if already dates exist
- Your questions are not clear. Informations for the dating are indispensable.
- absolutely necessary, with radiocarbon, dendro datings as well
- Dated material could be developed so that you could choose from different options instead of free text.

Result

- presetting of condition e.g. “sf” should be possible for a whole project or at least feature; “Mikrorest-Probe” obsolete
- Differentiation between glume basis and spiklet forks is missing (es wäre besser, Hüllspelzenbasen und Ährchengabeln getrennt zu zählen)
- when selecting “fraction” the entry remembers the choice, this is not the case for “preservation type”, but will be very useful especially as now per deafold takes charred remain, but if working with sub-fossil one needs to click it all the time
- especially when entering fragments of weight or numbers - linkage with the corresponding text in the manual
- Your questions are not clear. Informations for the results are indispensable.
- absolutely necessary

Missing thesaurus

Question: Do you think that the Theasuri of the selection fields contain enough information, or would additions be necessary?

Answer: (one answer is possible)

- The fields contain enough information.
- Minor adjustments are necessary
- The fields must be completely revised
- No answer

Comment:

- exceptionally it should be possible to add terms if necessary
- the related tables have to be so flexible, that in case in some years something really missing can be added
- I think for European context and even mostly Near East up to Egypt the treasury and good and already have been negotiated between the users. The communities for Asia and South America etc. probably will need to work further

PCODE

Question: Is the current PCODE list sufficient?

Answer: (one answer is possible)

- Yes
- No, individual entries are missing
- No, entire plant groups, e.g. from other regions, are missing (please provide examples as comments)
- No (please comment)
- No answer

Comment:

- Even northern Africa and temperate Asia pose difficulties. The flora only works at best in central Europe... You cannot enter the wild ancestors of cereals, etc
- So for example we only have *Alnus glutinosa* (L.) Gaertn. - very frustrating that we have to score it *Alnus incana*/ *glutinosa*. Main problem is you have not adopted Stace - do mind if it isn't 2019 (4th edn.) - most specialists are using 2010. However ecology data is available (and digitally) linked to 2019 4th edn. of Stace
- Viele Doppelbestimmungen sind in der soziologischen Liste nicht vorhanden (translated by authors: Many duplicate determinations are not included in the sociological list)
- The same: doe Europe, Near East and Northe Africa shall be OK
- It is too time-consuming to get new taxa added
- There are always PCODES missing. Sometimes PCODES of individual plants (e.g. *Dasyphyrum villosum*, *Lallemantia iberica*, *Vaccaria hispanica*). More often PCODES of similar looking plant remains, also depending on the preservation status (e.g. *Scrophularia/Verbascum*, *Bolboschoenus/Schoenoplectus*, *Triticum dicocum/monococum*/"new-type" (*timopheevi*)).
- for work in Southern France species were missing, e.g. *Amaranthaceae* halophytes like *Salicornia* are incomplete some species like *Piper* sp. are missing in our group, we also like to use ArboDat for the semi-quantitative recording of preservation (using preservation indicators), so it would be important for us to either be able to introduce these again ourselves or having them introduced
- For practical reasons at the moment PCODE/species from different continents, e.g. Europe and Africa (and the related data) are handled by the colleagues in separate PCODE-lists and databases. This practice prevents too long and confusing lists and mixing of results you will never compare
- exceptionally it should be possible to add species if necessary; one should not mix different flora sets of different countries.
- problem with using an older Flora for Great Britain. Also some inflexibility with taxa - so we have

Alnus glutinosa (L.) Gaertn. only in Britain post-Mesolithic - but ArboDAT only gives us the option *A. incana*/ *glutinosa*.

- This is mainly some plant “pairs” and sea weed. Several northern plants are missing (but we really don’t find these neither).

Data evaluation

Is Data Evaluation necessary

Question: Is the section of data evaluation a necessary part of ArboDat for you?

Answer: (One answer is possible)

- Yes
- Nice feature, but not necessary
- No
- No answer

Used functions

Comment by the authors: This question was only visible to users who have chosen to use this section.

Question: Which functions do you use in the “Data Evaluation” section?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Number of Pieces/Weight
- Frequency
- Concentration
- Taxon Search

Total: 22 answers

Report

Is Site report necessary

Question: Is the site report area a necessary part of ArboDat for you?

Answer: (One answer is possible)

- Yes, site reports are absolutely necessary
- Site reports are useful, but not absolutely necessary
- A site report would be important but I can't use it in its current format
- No, I hardly/never use it
- No answer

Used functions

Comment by the authors: This question was only visible to users who have chosen to use this section

Question: Which part of Site-Report do you use?

Answer: (Multiple answers are possible)

- Differentiated per Period
- Summarized

In total: 15 person answered the question.

Differentiated per period: 12

Summarized: 12

Statistical Analysis and Data Viewer

Question: One idea for the change from ArboDat to ArboDat+ is to separate the programme for recording the data from the evaluation and the report section and also to create an ArboDat viewer available as an open source web app and which could also be expanded by the community. The viewer should include the functions of the report and the data evaluation, extended by graphical displays and statistical analysis. This could be developed collaboratively on the basis of R. The disadvantage would be that the data for analysis (initially) need to be transferred via an exchange file. How do you find such a solution?

Answer: (One answer is possible)

- Good
- Neutral
- Bad - Data evaluation should remain an integral component
- Bad - Site report should remain an integral component
- Bad - Data evaluation and site report should remain an integral component
- Data evaluation and report are obsolete
- No answer

Perspective of ArboDat

Question: In order to be able to publish the data online, a closer connection to the data publisher Pangaea is planned. Data from ArboDat+ can be easily uploaded there and published open access with little effort.

Answer: (One answer is possible)

- I like that idea
- Online publication is obsolete
- other
- No answer

Comment:

- next to Pangea, there shall be other options - like Neotoma, GFZ, SEAD etc. and the archives shall be able to communicate with each other
- I use another repository
- no use of it, data transfer complicate
- I like the idea, but at the moment Pangaea appears not be a good platform for this.

Final comments

- We need ArboDat in its full functionality. For the team in Hemmenhofen it is important next to the data entry, to obtain easy and on daily basis overview of the data (as now through the visible tables and pre programmed evaluations and reports). We consider R and SQL etc. . . solution as not suitable for “normal” users i.e. not familiar with coding etc. We use the program every day - not only for data storage and management, but also for evaluation, merging of datasets, exchange with other labs, even simple checking if there are enough seeds for c-14. Thus we are happy to store our data in ArboDat but also to use it as a tool for visualisation, reporting and research. Without the existing functions, our work will become very difficult. To make the data from ArboDat in their full capacity storable and exchangeable with archives/repositories is a good initiative, but probably shall not be considered so narrow and apart of Pangea also other options like Neotoma or GFZ or SEAD shall be considered. Interoperability and communication are also of advantage to attract more user. I am very happy for this initiative to contact us and collect the community feedback and will be happy to learn on the outcome and to support the efforts and further steps with what I can.
- I think the data evaluation should have the option of not using the ecological classification of central Europe. Even when you work in Spain this is totally useless and I have heard of many people working in different areas of Europe saying that they rearrange the tables completely. There should be an option dividing the plants into crops, wild plants and Varia. It is also a shame that we enter entire remains and fragments and this is not seen in the final tables. This should be the choice of the researcher. It would be great if the new software could count taxa (correctly. . .) because this always takes a lot of time.
- I think my main frustration having attended a ‘training session’ and having provided data (all in my own time/ unpaid) - is I’m still not able to use ArboDAT and I still don’t have access to data from other sites. Working commercially - saving time is a huge issue. I do not understand why it isn’t possible to have this data available if uploaded without embargo for other specialists to see. It also would help prevent my own work being so insular (largely England only - biased to digitally available publications I suspect) - because I just don’t have the time available to do more than compare my site with others in the county I’m working in, maybe in the wider region. Would love to be in a situation where I can say taxon from X period has also found at x many sites in England (possibly beyond) according to ArboDAT data (consulted 202?) - and hope this endeavour can make it happen. I thank you for attempting it anyway.
- I don’t use the button “data survey” but I use very much the tables themselves to look into the data. For that I use “filter”, “search” or I do own small queries. It’s absolutely necessary for our work to look into the data, this can’t be separated from the recording.
- Thank you for all the work on ArboDat so far. It is a great tool.
- I believe that a separation of the features in the database is bad, separating, making people use R instead is not user friendly at all. More data will be added and used if you make it easy to use and to learn as a new user.
- -I think that as long as the evaluation and report function are possible in one version of ArboDat (offline) you could make one specifically for data entry online (ArboDat viewer), that would be open access (open access database just for entries for example). -An open access database would be very nice, where people can share their database. A nice add one would be if you could do the analysis online but you could possibly also download the data and do it in the offline version. -Having the evaluation and report function, I always found a large plus of ArboDat. -with two separate things: your link between the data and the analysis might get more loose (arboDat +)
- Thank you for this initiative and success for your work!
- About the part “Perspective of ArboDat”, I would welcome a combination with R, but I still think it should be possible to have an initial evaluation (like concentration) in the program itself - or at least without exchange file (our database is very big)
- Here my first comments; a more detailed discussion will be possible only when the concept of ArboDat+ has been more clarified: All hitherto existing interactive ArboDat functionalities are needed for our standardized data archiving, scientific archaeobotanical work, data exchange and data documentation and as a basis for data visualization. As most users (like myself) are not familiar with R, Java or other

programming languages we are not able (and do not have the time) to program individual queries. This has to be provided by the ArboDat+ team. The (structural) tables of ArboDat include German, English and French terms used by the users since decades. Therefore, care has to be taken, that these terms are not changed. The same holds true for the botanical names connected with the PCODE (see ArboDat manuals). All drop-down menus have to be kept as well to provide a user-friendly data entry etc. Access to the data tables has to be warranted, to be able to check and change data entries. Data entry and the different entry levels project, feature, sample, results per fraction etc. have to be provided 1:1 analogue to the recent ArboDat-version including carbon and other dating, the calculation functions and linked ecological data (see ArboDat manuals). A very important point will be in the end the individual, loss-free data transfer from old to new ArboDat software “at the push of a button”. Nobody has the time to enter data again. As for online publishing: A variety of repositories are available at the moment. The final decision has to be taken by the different authors and institutions. My data are located open access at GFZ Data Services, which is a repository for research data and scientific software across the Earth System Sciences, hosted at GFZ. They are archived in the ArboDat 2016 datacentre, see GFZ Data Services - Metadata Portal (gfz-potsdam.de)

- some questions are not asked open; some questions not clear; only 14, not 15 questions; Questionnaire not really standardized; it seems that the result is already there??; Data transfers should be simple and automated, no duplicate entries; one should extract data without any further programming necessary
- I think efforts to make data sharing between researchers are very worthwhile and congratulate you on your project
- yes, I have received permission from Museum of Archaeology London to participate in a discussion forum as we’d like to be in a situation where we could upload data to ArboDAT (and access other specialist’s data).
- Thanks for letting us use ArboDat, it is a great tool!

Significance of survey results for the development of ArboDat+

Content redesign

The main purpose of the survey is to determine the priorities for the new content concept of ArboDat+. These will be summarized once again on the basis of the questions:

Language

The survey showed that the English and German versions of ArboDat are the most popular ones being used. The comments point out that the English version in particular can be used by the entire community.

As the program is currently multilingual, this should continue to exist. On top, adding further languages shall be possible - although the translation will then have to be carried out by regional representatives of the community.

Section

When asked about the use of the individual program components of ArboDat, it is clear that data entry and evaluation are used above all. However, more than half of the users also create site reports or use Data Survey.

This makes it clear that all these areas need to be taken into account in a new concept.

Missing values

When asked about missing points or points that need to be changed when recording data, it became clear that in many areas, minor changes are desired in order to make work easier. These mainly relate to field values and lengths. The larger problems identified include, for example, the input of different fraction sizes, the assignment of dates not only to individual samples but also to features and the revision of the input of dates.

When adapting the software, a special focus will once again be placed on this.

Missing entries in the thesauri and in PCODE

The survey also asked whether there were any missing entries in the individual selection fields and the PCODE. This revealed a different picture. While only a small number of changes are desired for the selection fields, there is a high demand for PCODEs.

It is therefore planned to store the lists for selection fields on a central thesaurus server, where changes are made available to all users. The same is to be done for the PCODE, where it will be possible to store various terminologies that can then be selected by users. This enables quality control when expanding content and at the same time simple adaptation when changing taxonomies. At the same time, it enables internationalization so that it can also be used by researchers in different regions of the world or other specialist areas. In both cases, the changes are versioned and stored with a DOI in order to enable citation and track changes.

Which functions of the individual software areas of “Data evaluation” and “Site report” are used and are they important for ArboDat?

Data recording is of course the basis of ArboDat, but data evaluation and site report are also used. While satisfaction with “Data evaluation” is high, it is recognized that “Site report” is a not unimportant component, although some users cannot use it in the current way.

The adaptation to the user needs of these programme components is to be determined in a further step in the ArboDat+ forum.

Future prospects and fundamental changes to the software

The last two questions in the survey focused on the basic integration of components that do not relate to data input. This shows that a small majority of users see these program components as an integral part of the software itself. The remaining participants can also imagine outsourcing them to a second software tool. The creation of a simpler data publication option is viewed very favorably. Some comments point out that this should not be done exclusively with Pangaea.

It is planned, that data publication will be facilitated for the upload to the platform Pangaea, however exporting and submitting your data to other data publishers will still be possible as well. Thanks to the intensive collaboration between Pangaea and the ArboDat+ development team, there will be a standardized and therefore very low-threshold option for publishing the data, which will also be free of charge. Based on the results, the approach of transferring the existing evaluation options to the new software is being pursued. However, it will probably not be possible to address all the changes expressed by the community. It is therefore being considered to create an online platform with evaluation tools, which will also be made available open access and thus offer the possibility of making further evaluation tools (further) developed by the users available to everyone. This makes it easier to integrate new evaluation and reporting functions. Some comments were apparently based on a misunderstanding: future users do not need to have any programming experience. However, people who do have such knowledge can contribute to the further development. An open and structured data format would be used to transfer the data into an evaluation tool so that this is easy for the user.

Outlook

In addition to adapting the content components, the technical side of ArboDat is also being redesigned. By renewing the database structure, a higher degree of data security and longevity will be achieved. Also, adaptation to modern requirements in the field of research data management will be performed. The use of open systems and the associated abandonment of MS Access will put an end to program dependency and support more flexible and future-oriented software development. The entire new concept will be made available open access after completion and offers the opportunity to develop further adaptations and extensions by the users. With this, we hope to reach even more archaeobotanists and potential users in the future who will use this software. Current users of ArboDat can of course continue to use the current version of the program and manage their data as usual. However, following the successful redesign, there will be no further development of the Access-based version.

This work aims at a significant contribution to the harmonisation, long-term archiving and publication of archaeobotanical data. It will offer an internationally available platform for flexible and efficient reuse of the data. The resulting software application service will enable its users to register and analyse archaeobotanical data and related metadata in a standard database in order to make them freely accessible to the scientific community, especially national and international archaeobotanists and scientists in related disciplines (cultural and natural sciences).

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